

THE STUDY OF NEW NATIONAL INSTITUTIONAL RANKING SYSTEM USING ABCD FRAMEWORK

Dr. P. S. Aithal*, V. T. Shailashree & P. M. Suresh Kumar*****

Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, Karnataka

Abstract:

The institutions of higher education in India are in need of infusion of quality and clarity on the approach of building world-class educational institutions in the Indian context and environment. New benchmarks of quality need to be defined to help overall system to move up on the quality spectrum. Research assessment and national ranking of Indian educational institutions can play an important role in improving performance and quality of academic institutions. Recently, the Ministry of Human Resource Development, Govt. of India has identified various criteria and parameters that have global appeal e.g. research output, research impact, learning environment, etc. This framework called National Institutional Ranking Framework has also considered parameters like infrastructure, facilities for differently-abled persons, percentage of students from other states and other countries; percentage of women students and faculty, and percentage of economically and disadvantaged students. The framework has also given weightage to the sports and extra-curricular facilities available in the campuses of universities, which supports on overall development of students in a university. In this paper we have analyzed "National Institutional Ranking System" for higher educational institutions as a novel performance evaluation system using our recently developed analyzing framework called ABCD technique. Based on four constructs Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages, this system consider all determinant issues in key areas through analyzing the major issues and identifying the critical constituent elements.

Index Terms: ABCD Analysis Framework, National Institutional Ranking Framework & Factors Affecting Ranking Framework

1. Introduction:

Institutional effectiveness is the systematic and ongoing process of collecting, analyzing and acting on data and information relating to the goals and outcomes developed to support the higher educational institutions mission and purpose. Institutional effectiveness is oriented towards measuring the performance and using those performances to aid in decision-making and improvement. Institutional effectiveness is a cyclical process in which continuous improvements and refinements on goals and methods are planned in a continuous basis. The institutions of higher education in India are in need of infusion of quality and clarity on the approach of building world-class educational institutions in the Indian context and environment. New benchmarks of quality need to be defined to help overall system to move up on the quality spectrum [1]. Research assessment and national ranking of Indian educational institutions can play an important role in improving performance and quality of academic institutions. The higher educational ranking system encourages quality improvement initiatives by Institutions, Improves student enrolment both in terms of quality and quantity, Helps the Institution in securing necessary funds, Encourages institutions to compete with other similar institutions, Enhances employability of graduates, Facilitates transnational recognition of degrees and mobility of graduates and professionals, Motivates faculty to participate actively in academic and related Institutional / departmental activities, Supports high quality research, Helps create sound and challenging academic environment in the Institution, and Contributes to

social and economic development of the country by producing high quality man power. Institutional ranking is a global practice and its need has been felt by various countries for various purposes like: Funding decisions, Accountability of institutions to stake holders, Encouraging self improvement initiatives by institutions, and quality assurance of educational programme. The institution which gets better rank in ranking process will come to know its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges, will get a sense of direction and identity, will provide society with reliable information on quality of education offered, and get opportunity to collaborate with similar higher educational institutions in abroad.

2. National Institutional Ranking Framework:

Recently, National Institutional Ranking Framework [2] developed by the Ministry of Human Resource Development, Govt. of India has identified various criteria and parameters that have global appeal e.g. research output, research impact, learning environment, etc. has also considered parameters like infrastructure, facilities for differently-abled persons, percentage of students from other states and other countries; percentage of women students and faculty, and percentage of economically and disadvantaged students. The framework has also given weightage to the sports and extra-curricular facilities available in the campuses of universities, which, supports on overall development of a student in a university/college. The five criteria with overall weightage and their internal parameters with internal weightage are summarised as follows:

(i) Teaching, Learning and Resources (TLR):

TLR has overall 40 % weightage with four parameters. These parameters with internal weightage is given by:

- ✓ Faculty – Student Ratio – 30 % internal weightage.
- ✓ Faculty with PhD and Experience – 30 % internal weightage.
- ✓ Library and Laboratory Facilities - 30 % internal weightage.
- ✓ Sports Facilities and Extra-Curricular Activities – 10 % internal weightage.

(ii) Research Productivity, Impact and IPR:

This criteria has 20% overall weightage with three parameters. These parameters with internal weightage is given by:

- ✓ Publications - 45 % internal weightage.
- ✓ Citations - 45 % internal weightage.
- ✓ IPR – 10 % internal weightage.

(iii) Graduation Outcome:

This criteria has 15% overall weightage with two parameters. These parameters with internal weightage is given by:

- ✓ University Exam Performance - 50 % internal weightage.
- ✓ Competitive Examination: - 50 % internal weightage.

(iv) Outreach and Inclusivity:

This criteria has 15% overall weightage with two parameters. These parameters with internal weightage is given by:

- ✓ Continuing Education, Services – 25 % internal weightage.
- ✓ Percentage of Students from Other States & Countries – 25 % internal weightage.
- ✓ Percentage of Women Students and Faculty – 20 % internal weightage.
- ✓ Percentage of Economically and Socially Disadvantaged Students – 20 % internal weightage.
- ✓ Facilities for Differently Abled Persons – 10 % internal weightage.

(v) Perception:

This criteria has 10% overall weightage with two parameters. These parameters with internal weightage is given by:

- ✓ Process for Peer Rating in Category (Brand) – 50 % internal weightage.
- ✓ Application to Seat Ratio - 50 % internal weightage.

3. Methodology of NIRF:

Methodology involves defining a set of metrics for ranking of universities and colleges based on the parameters. These parameters are organized into five broad categories that have been further grouped into a number of sub-categories. Each broad category has an overall weightage assigned to it. Within each category, the sub-categories also have an appropriate weightage distribution. In this process, first identify the relevant data needed to suitably measure the performance score under each sub-category. Emphasis has been laid on identifying data that is easy to generate and easy to verify, if needed, in the overall interest of transparency. Suitable metric is then proposed, based on this data, which computes a score under each sub-category. The sub-category scores are then added to obtain scores for each individual category. The overall score is computed based on the weights allotted to each category. The overall score can take a maximum value of 100. The institutions can then be rank-ordered based on their scores.

Optimum Requirements for Better Rank:

- ✓ In case of faculty-student ratio, assessment will be based on the ratio of number of regular faculty members in the Institute and total sanctioned/approved intake considering all full-time Programs. Benchmark ratio is 1:10 to score maximum marks.
- ✓ The faculty members with doctorate degree and the average experience required for maximum marks are 95% and 15 years respectively.
- ✓ Considerable amount of annual spending on Library and Laboratory for procurement and maintenance will give maximum score for Library, Laboratory and sports.
- ✓ Maximum publications and citations for articles, books and patents published per faculty as an average to all faculty of the institution decides the research related score.
- ✓ Student performance in University exams are optimized in such a way that at least 80% students should graduate in minimum time to score maximum Marks.
- ✓ Based on gender equality requirement, if 50% women students and 20% women faculty and two women as Institute Head or in the Governing Board expected to score maximum marks.
- ✓ Out of total student strength, 50% economically and socially disadvantaged students should be admitted to score maximum marks.

Based on scores given in Teaching, Learning and Resources, Research Productivity, Impact and IPR, Graduation Outcome, Outreach and Inclusivity, and Society Perception, an institution gets rank at national level. Lower the rank better is the institution in terms of its grade, quality and service to the society. In this paper we have analyzed the various features of "National Institutional Ranking System" for higher educational institutions as a new system using our recently developed business model & concept analyzing framework called ABCD technique.

4. ABCD Analysis Framework:

ABCD is an acronym that stands for Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages. Application of ABCD analysis results in an organized list of a business

advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages in a systematic matrix. The entire framework is divided under various issues/area of focus and various business deployment factors affecting the business/concept can be identified and analyzed under each issue by identifying suitable critical effective element. This analyzing technique being simple, gives guideline to identify and analyze the effectiveness of any business model and new concepts developed. In this research, we suggested the business concept analysis (ABCD) framework for evaluating an institutional ranking strategy. This study is meaningful in suggesting integrated perspective analyzing ranking strategy in the frame of reference of organization, academics, student, faculty, administration, infrastructure and learning resources, and other stake holders' issues. Based on four constructs Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages, of this system consider all determinants in key areas through analyzing the major issues and identifying the critical constituent elements. The result supported the logic of using ABCD analyzing technique in any System performance evaluation.

Various analyzing framework are mentioned in the literature and are used to study a concept, system, idea or strategy in business management. This include SWOT, SLEPT (social, legal, economic, political, technical) (de Witt and Meyer, 1998) [2], and the BSC (Balanced Score Card) analysis, which can be used to identify an organization's strategic needs, none provides a direct mechanism to prioritize the needs and convert them into operational processes or to then translate those processes into a specification that can be used to develop or acquire supportive software systems. In contrast to this, other analytical techniques such as Porter's (1985) [3] Value Chain Analysis (VCA), facilitate the analysis of processes within a company but do not provide an easy mechanism to link these to high-level business objectives. According to Wu (1992) [4], good framework should guide toward a method or solution uniquely suitable to the particular situation in question. Lee and Ko (2000) [5] proposed a framework for strategic business analysis by integrating SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats), balanced score card (Kaplan, 1992) [6] and quality function deployment. Various techniques are used to analyze individual characteristics or organizational effectiveness & strategies in a given environment like SWOT analysis, SWOC analysis, PEST analysis, McKinsey 7S framework, ICDT model, Portor's five force model etc. But there is a need for simple but systematic analyzing technique for business models analysis.

ABCD analysing framework is recently developed by Aithal P.S. et. al. [7] to analyze any business model/concept and to study its effectiveness in providing value to its stake holders and sustainable profit through expected revenue generation. Application of ABCD analysis results in an organized list of a business advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages in a systematic matrix. The entire framework is divided under various issues/area of focus and various business deployment factors affecting the business/concept can be identified and analyzed under each issue by identifying suitable critical effective element. This analyzing technique being simple, gives guideline to identify and analyze the effectiveness of any business model and new concepts developed.

Reshma et. al. [8-9], have analysed the characteristics of "Working from Home" e-business model using 'ABCD Analysis Technique'. Based on various factors which decides the Working from Home system, a model of various factors and their constituent critical elements affecting under organizational objectives, employers point of view, employees point of view, customers/students point of view, environmental/societal point of view and system requirements are derived by a

qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method. It is found that the factors supporting advantages and benefits are more effective compare to constraints and disadvantages of this model, so that working from home model may become more popular from the prospective of employers and employees in the organization in the future.

Recently ABCD analysis framework is used for analysing Black ocean strategy concept [10 -11]. The various factors & their constituent critical factors affecting the BOS concept adopted in some of the business organizations for quick relief from the problems are identified for organizational point of view, administrative point of view, employee point of view, operational point of view, business point of view and external issues point of view are determined under the four constructs - advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages.

ABCD analysis framework is also used for analysing National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) accreditation process on higher education institutions [12]. The various features of the NAAC accreditation system is evaluated based on identifying and analyzing the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of some of the chosen issues like organizational issues, faculty performance issues, student development/progression issues, social/environmental/community engagement issues, infrastructure and learning resources, and issues on innovations creativity and best practices. The affecting factors under these issues were found out using focus group method and the constituent critical elements under each factor are identified. The results supported the logic of using ABCD analyzing technique in any System/concept performance evaluation. ABCD analysis framework is also used for analysing an innovative Stage Model in higher education system [13-14]. In this paper the various features of Stage Model intervention technique are analysed through the ABCD analyzing framework. The results supported the logic of using ABCD analyzing technique for any system/concept performance evaluation.

A general guideline on using ABCD analysis framework is suggested in the paper "Study on ABCD Analysis Technique for Business Models, Business Strategies, Operating Concepts & Business Systems' [15]. This paper also contain the procedure of prioritizing the affecting factors to calculate the scores and hence weightage to the affecting factors and critical constituent elements. In this paper, ABCD analysing framework is compared with other known analyzing techniques like SWOC, Competitive Profile Matrix (CPM) analysis, EFE & IFE Matrices, BCG analysing frameworks, Porter's Five Forces Model, and PESTLE Analysis.

In this paper we have analyzed the various features of National Institutional Ranking System for higher educational institutions as a new system using our recently developed business model & concept analyzing framework called ABCD technique. Based on four constructs Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages, of this system consider all determinants in key areas through analyzing the major issues and identifying the critical constituent elements. The result supported the logic of using ABCD analyzing technique in any System performance evaluation.

5. ABCD Analysis of NIRF:

Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages (ABCD) of a System can be used to analyze and understand the model/system in an effective way. As per this analysis technique [15 -20] the effectiveness of a business model/concept/system can be studied by identifying and analyzing the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages by considering various issues like Organizational Issues, Academic Issues, Student Issues, Faculty Issues, Issues on Administration, Infrastructure and

Learning resources, and Other stake holders issues as in the block diagram of issues affecting the NIRF System and is shown in fig. 1. The various factors contributing under the four identified constructs like advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages are derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method [21-22] and the constituent critical elements supporting these factors are identified. Table 1 shows the framework of ABCD model in terms of advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages in terms of determinant issues mentioned above and the key issues coming under them [15].

Figure 1: Block diagram of issues affecting the NIRF system as per ABCD framework.
 Table 1: Perspectives for the Determinant Issues

Criteria	Organizational issues	Academic issues	Student issues	Faculty issues	Issues on administration, infrastructure & learning resources	Other stake holder issues
Teaching, learning and resources	Educational powerhouse	Educational catalyst	Educational inducement	Educational strength	Educational supplements	Educational support
Research productivity, impact and IPR	Knowledge centre	Knowledge dissemination	Knowledge utilization	Knowledge creation	Knowledge providers	Knowledge gain
Graduation outcome	Exam Takers	Exam performers	Exam beneficiaries	Exam improvers	Exam conductors	Exam appreciators
Outreach and inclusivity	Integration facilitators	Integrationists	Integration contenders	Integration providers	Integration enhancers	Integration
Perception	Image builders	Image setters	Image providers	Image carriers	Image contributors	Image sharers

Table 2: Analysis of new national ranking system using ABCD framework

Particulars	Perspectives	Advantages	Benefits	Constraints	Disadvantages
Organizational issues					
Teaching learning and resources	Educational power house	Increased efficiency	Growth of the organization	Scarcity of opportunity	Maintain optimum levels
Research productivity, impact and IPR	Knowledge center	Pro-research orientation	Creation of new knowledge	Require effort	Slow to materialize
Graduation Outcome	Exam takers	Better performers	High achievements	Motivation	Varying interests
Outreach and Inclusivity	Integration facilitators	Civic responsibility	Integration	Low priority	Limited attainment
Perception	Image builders	Positive image	Brand building	Slow process	No immediate gain
Academic issues					
Teaching learning and resources	Educational catalyst	Action plan and teaching aids	Enhanced learning practices	Teacher-learner incompatibility	Continuous improvement
Research productivity, impact and IPR	Knowledge dissemination	Creativity and innovation encouraged	Emphasis on research orientation and learning culture	Risk taking	Interest generation
Graduation Outcome	Exam performers	Increased employability	Acquisition of skills	Inadequate fundamentals	High ambitions
Outreach and Inclusivity	Integrationists	Service orientation	Building institution-community network	Resource constraints	Unrealistic expectation
Perception	Image setters	Higher standards	Outstanding quality	Collective effort	Less forthcoming
Student Issues					
Teaching learning and resources	Educational inducement	Enriched campus life	All round development	Diminishing student interest	Optimum priority
Research productivity, impact and IPR	Knowledge utilization	Try out something original	New creations	Fear of gradation	Monotony
Graduation Outcome	Exam beneficiaries	More entrepreneurs	Unemployment reduced	Low preference	Success not assured
Outreach and Inclusivity	Integration contenders	Service commitment	Binding institution-community network	Resource constraints	Unrealistic expectation
Perception	Image providers	Effective grievance and counseling mechanism	Effective service	Diluted student initiative	Grievances persisting
Faculty Issues					
Teaching learning and resources	Educational strength	Diverse faculty	Better adaptability	Student-teacher gap	Limited exposure
Research	Knowledge	Rewarding	Maintaining	Building	Possibility of

productivity, impact and IPR	creation	and encouraging potentials	efficiency	long term research goals	errors
Graduation Outcome	Exam improvers	Beyond syllabus	Result orientation	Conventional mindset	Lack of examples
Outreach and Inclusivity	Integration providers	Interaction with society	Service to society	Curriculum gaps	Examination constraints
Perception	Image carriers	Empowered faculty	Role performance	Motivation	Reduced interest
Issues on Administration Infrastructure And Learning resources					
Teaching learning and resources	Educational supplements	Teacher – student ratio	Personal attention	Diverse backgrounds	Constant up gradation
Research productivity, impact and IPR	Knowledge providers	New experiments	Better examples	Limited initiative	No target for research output
Graduation Outcome	Exam conductors	Grooming students in all walks of life	Lifelong changes	Active learning	Additional effort
Outreach and Inclusivity	Integration enhancers	Knowledgeable and Enlightened citizens	Healthy and socially responsible society	Existing diversity	Maintaining Ethics and Values
Perception	Image contributors	Latest and modern methods	Innovations	Cost of experimenting	Risk of result
Other Stakeholders Issues					
Teaching learning and resources	Educational support	Offer choice	Challenging	Prioritizing	Stay focused
Research productivity, impact and IPR	Knowledge gain	Critical thinking	Questioning ability	Limited scope	Low support
Graduation Outcome	Exam appreciators	More job aspirants	Wide knowledge pool	Attracting Talent	Retaining talent
Outreach and Inclusivity	Integration	Addressing cross cutting issues	Fulfilling existential priorities	Magnitude of the problem	Tiny and piecemeal efforts
Perception	Image sharers	Community benefited	Contributes to nation building	Skeptical attitude	Apathy

6. Critical Constituent Elements as per ABCD Model:

As per ABCD framework, the factors affecting under organizational, Administrative, Academic, Students, and Other stakeholders’ issues for National Institutional Ranking Framework are identified. The critical constituent elements of these factors are listed under the four constructs - advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of the ABCD technique and tabulated in tables 3 to 6.

Table 3: Advantages of new national ranking system

Organisational issues	Improved efficiency	Conservation of resources
		Utilization of resources
	Pro-research orientation	Creativity and Innovation
		Pursuit of learning
	Better performers	Intensive coaching
		Transparent evaluations
	Civic responsibility	Concern for fellowmen
		Passion for service

	Positive image	Vision and mission
		Quality standards followed
Academic issues	Action plan and teaching aids	Commitment to work
		Proper planning and implementation
	Creativity and innovation encouraged	Open mindedness
		Culture of learning
	Increased employability	Demonstrate talent
		Competitiveness
	Service orientation	Commitment
	Response to context	
	Higher standards	Consistency
		Pursuit
Student Issues	Enriched campus life	Well groomed students
		Desire to perform
	Try out something original	Encouragement
		Inner drive
	More entrepreneurs	Face challenges
		Optimism
	Service commitment	Good people relationships
		Develop sense of corporate citizenship
	Effective grievance and counseling mechanism	Trusted initiatives
		Inclination to utilize
Faculty Issues	Diverse faculty	Purposive recruitment
		Ability to adapt
	Rewarding and encouraging potentials	Performance management mechanism
		Acknowledge contributions
	Beyond syllabus	Unconventional attitude
		Approaches
	Interaction with society	Leadership
	Sense of direction	
	Empowered faculty	Setting example
		Readiness to change
Issues on Administration, Infrastructure and Learning resources	Teacher –student ratio	Conducive policies
		Capacity to handle complexity
	New experiments	Initiatives
		Innovations
	Grooming students in all walks of life	Varied exposure
		Acquisition of multiple skills
	Knowledgeable and Enrichment citizens	Positive learning
		Sense of responsibility
	Latest and modern methods	Experimenting and improving
		Accepting new trends
Other Stakeholders Issues	Offer Choices	More courses
		Designer pedagogy
	Critical thinking	Objective and non-conventional
		Questioning spirit
	More job aspirants	Employability skills
		Multiple choice and option
	Addressing cross cutting issues	Perception of issues
	Ability to handle issues	
	Community benefitted	Value result
		Share benefits

Table 4: Benefits of new national ranking system

Organisational issues	Growth of the organization	Increased size
		Expansion of functions
	Creation of new knowledge	Shared ideas
		Enhanced creativity
	High achievements	Redefined goal
		Concerted effort
	Integration	Path finder
		Unwieldy task
	Brand building	Display uniqueness
		Outsmart competition
Academic issues	Enhanced learning practices	Learning resources
		Quality standards
	Emphasis on research orientation and learning culture	Collective involvement
		Inherent interest
	Acquisition of skills	Inclusion of skill enhancers
		Matching industry requirements
	Building institution-community network	Tie up with CSR activities
		Identifying solutions to community problems
Outstanding quality	Persistent effort	
	Desire to be different	
Student Issues	All round development	Improved participation
		Increased competencies
	New creations	Demonstrate usefulness
		Display advantage
	Unemployment reduced	Expanded choices
		Extended opportunities
	Binding institution-community network	Sustainability
		Student friendly activities
Effective service	Student partnership	
	Personalized services	
Faculty Issues	Better adaptability	Promote unity
		Favour collaboration
	Maintaining efficiency	Frequent feedback
		Encouraging publications
	Result oriented	Believe in action
		Think beyond confines
	Service to society	Readiness
		Means and resources
Role performance	Role clarity	
	Fixed norms	
Issues on Administration, Infrastructure and Learning resources	Personal attention	Teacher interest
		Teacher-student relation
	Better examples	Proven result
		Lasting impressions
	Lifelong changes	Permanent impact
		Show difference
	Healthy and socially responsible Society	High living standards
		Reduced gap between rich and poor
Innovations	Replicability	
	User friendly	
Other Stakeholders Issues	Challenging	New pathways
		Uniqueness
	Thinking encouraged	Response to feed back
		Critical evaluation

	Wide knowledge pool	Learning and sharing Specialized knowledge
	Fulfilling existential priorities	Collective action Ensuring survival
	Contributes to nation building	Value and ethics
		Peace and order

Table 5: Constraints of new national ranking system

Organizational issues	Scarcity of opportunity	Improper planning
		Unhealthy competition
	Require effort	Focused growth
		Individual contribution
	Motivation	Timeliness
		Appropriate manner
Low priority	Willingness to shoulder responsibility	
	Create interest	
Slow process	Time tested process	
	Public appeal	
Academic issues	Teacher- learner incompatibility	Generation gap
		Learning environment
	Risk taking behavior	Learning from mistakes
		Assuming responsibilities
	Inadequate foundation	Poor background
		Individual differences
Resource constraints	Insufficient allocation	
	Increased overhead	
Collective effort	Strength of togetherness	
	Insufficient attention	
Student Issues	Diminishing student interest	Aptitude
		Attitude
	Fear of gradation	Open competition
		Transparent evaluation
	Low preference	Poor entrepreneurship
		Lack of support
Resource constraints	Expensive programmes	
	Dependence on fund	
Diluted student initiative	Passive beneficiaries	
	Misguided	
Faculty Issues	Student- teacher gap	Proper orientation
		Adoption of best practices
	Building long term research goals	Interest and enthusiasm
		Scope for benefit
	Conventional mindset	Grooming to time
		Growing with time
Curriculum gaps	Theory - practice divide	
	Reduced focus	
Motivation	Right attitude	
	Wrong mentality	
Issues on Administration, Infrastructure and Learning resources	Diverse backgrounds	Insensitivity
		Incapacity
	Limited initiative	Cost
		Pessimism
	Active learning	Limited enthusiasm
		Participation
Expanding diversities	Mutual discrimination	
	Tendency to stay away	
Cost of experimenting	Accountability	

		Poor leadership	
Other Stakeholders Issues	Prioritizing	Different considerations Ignorance	
	Limited scope	Low concern Not directly affected	
	Attracting talent	Otherwise pre-occupied Better prospects	
	Magnitude of the problem	Complex Incapability to address	
	Skeptical attitude		Poor experience
			Low awareness

Table 6: Disadvantages of new national ranking system

Organisational issues	Maintain optimum levels	Tendency to keep balance Precautions against adversities
	Slow to materialize	Growing organization Low prioritization
	Varying interest	Individual uniqueness Diversion to other activities
	Limited attainment	Complex community Divisive forces operating
	No immediate gain	Lasting results Long term benefits
Academic issues	Continuous improvement	Trial and error efforts Customized to requirement
	Interest generation	Difficult to address all issues Inhibitions
	High Ambitions	Limits to learning Diverse requirements
	Unrealistic expectation	Gigantic programmes Vested interest
	Less forthcoming	Takes time Generate interest
Student Issues	Optimum priority	Not utilizing opportunities Not reaching every body
	Monotony	Job enrichment Urge for creativity
	Success not assured	Individual differences Extent of involvement
	Unrealistic expectation	Short term interest Individual goals
	Grievances persisting	New Issues Unsettled issues
Faculty Issues	Limited exposure	Interactional opportunities Egalitarian outlook
	Possibility of errors	Unintentional bias Intentional discrimination
	Lack of examples	Uncommon practice Inability to appreciate
	Examination constraints	Pressure for academic learning Narrow focus
	Reduced interest	Reward system Acknowledge contributions
Issues on Administration, Infrastructure and Learning	Constant upgradation	Faculty development programmes Coaching and mentoring
	No target for research output.	Low concern Poor priority

resources	Maintaining Ethics and Values	Yield to pressures
		Erosion of values
	Risk of result	Uncertainty for investment
		Viability of innovations
Other Stakeholders Issues	Stay focused	Fluctuating job market
		Unsure of choice
	Low support	Diversity of views
		Politicization
	Retaining talent	Changing likes and dislikes
		Applying motivations l
	Tiny and piecemeal efforts	Fringe solutions
		Peripheral service
	Apathy	Low concern
		Limited reach

7. Conclusion:

We have studied the relevance objectives and the features of National Institutional Ranking Framework developed by Human Resource Development Division of Govt. of India as a ranking framework of higher education system. The NIRF supports the student’s progress towards enhancing their knowledge, skills, and experience. NIRF supports the complete progress and personal development of each individual student. The framework is able to cultivate a partnership particularly with parents, business and the community as a whole to support students learning and progress. NIRF also provide immediate solutions to the higher education requirements especially to innovate and progress viable models of quality learning. NIRF provides a comprehensive ranking suitable for higher educational institutions and it takes care of many small and subtle aspects comparable to quality assessment criterion of National Assessment and Accreditation Council.

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